

**STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES FOR SKIN BIOPSY SAMPLING,
PROCESSING, AND IMMUNOSTAINING.
SKIN BIOPSY LABORATORY, SAPIENZA UNIVERSITY OF ROME.**

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PUNCH BIOPSY SAMPLING:

Setting: Neurological consultancy room			
Tools	Instruments	Reagents	Equipment
Sterile gloves Sterile cloth 200cc Syringe Band-aids Sterile gauzes 10 ml Eppendorf	3 mm diameter Punch	Zamboni's solution Iodate solution Lidocaine Chlorhexidine	Refrigerator

- Ensure the patient signs the written consent form and verbally repeat the key information outlined in the informed consent.
- Prepare a 10 ml Eppendorf tube with 2 ml of Zamboni's solution. Write the patient's Name, Surname, Birthdate, Current date, and sampling site on the surface of the Eppendorf.
- Instruct the patient to lie on their left side if sampling the right leg (or vice versa).
- Place a sterile cloth under the leg being sampled.
- Mark the selected areas for skin biopsy (10 cm above the lateral malleolus and 20 cm below the antero-superior iliac spine).
- Cleanse the selected area at least three times with iodate solution, moving in circular motions from the center outwards, disinfecting a circular area of at least 15 cm in diameter around the sampling point. Finish with a final disinfection using a clear detergent, such as chlorhexidine.
- Inject 100cc of lidocaine (10mg/ml) into the center of the selected area.
- After injection, test pinprick sensitivity using the sterile syringe tip. Proceed with sampling if the patient reports loss of sensation or tactile sensation upon pricking. If pinprick sensitivity persists, recheck after one minute. If sensitivity remains, administer additional 100cc of lidocaine and repeat the sensitivity check.
- Once pinprick sensitivity is locally lost, proceed with sampling.
- Position the sterile 3 mm punch over the desired sampling point and gently but firmly push it into the skin using a rotating motion.
- Extract the punch from the skin and immerse it in the Eppendorf containing Zamboni's solution to release the biopsy.
- Place the Eppendorf in the refrigerator (+4°C).
- Apply pressure to the sampled area with a sterile gauze for three minutes to control bleeding.

- Cover the area with a band-aid.

SKIN BIOPSY PROCESSING, CUT, AND STORAGE:

Setting: Skin biopsy Lab			
Tools	Instruments	Reagents	Equipment
10 ml Eppendorf		Cryoprotectant	Freezer Refrigerator Cryostat

- Place the biopsy in Zamboni's fixative and store it in the refrigerator at +4°C for 6 hours. Fixation up to 24°C is consented under peculiar logistic circumstances.
- Rinse the tissue blocks twice with phosphate buffer (PB) for 10 minutes each.
- Transfer the skin biopsy to an Eppendorf tube filled with cryoprotectant (20% glycerol, 20% PB, 60% dH2O).
- Store the sample at -20°C in the freezer.
- When ready for cutting, remove the skin biopsy from cryoprotectant.
- Position the block on a cryostat support, cover it with inclusion medium and place it in the cryostat. Once frozen, begin cutting with a thickness setting of 50 microns.
- Meanwhile, prepare a 96-well plate filled with cryoprotectant.
- Place each cut skin section into a well.
- Decide whether to initiate immunostaining immediately or store the plate with cut sections at -20°C for further processing.

SKIN SECTIONS FREE-FLOATING IMMUNOSTAINING WITH INDIRECT IMMUNOFLUORESCENCE:

Indirect immunofluorescence double staining protocol for PGP9.5 and collagen IV, with PGP9.5 marking intraepidermal and dermal nerve fibers and collagen IV marking skin basal membrane.

Setting: Skin biopsy Lab			
Tools	Instruments	Reagent	Equipment
Glass slide baskets Nitrile gloves Adhesive tape Parafilm Indelible marker Fine tip brush Petri dish Disposable 96 wells plates Pliers Pasteur's pipette Cover slides Object slides	Pipette Automatic pipettor	PBS (phosphate buffer solution) Block solution Wash solution Fluorescence mounting medium 100% Ethanol 95% Ethanol	Logika hood Stereomicroscope Tilting agitator

- Label the bottom and top of a new plate and fill the first row of wells with PBS.
- Place the 3 sections of the biopsy into 3 consecutive wells of the plate containing PBS.

- Write the sample code at the top of the plate to identify the corresponding sections. This setup allows for processing 4 samples per plate, with each row containing 12 wells, each one containing one free-floating section.
- Put the plate on the tilting agitator for 5 minutes.
- Using an automatic pipettor, dispense 100µl of Block solution into each well of the second row of the plate. Using a Billau handle, transfer the sections from the first to the second row and let them soak on the tilting agitator for 60 minutes.
- Dispense 50µl of each of the two primary antibodies specified for the protocol into each well of the third row. Transfer the sections into the antibodies using the Billau handle. Place the plates on the agitator for 30-60 minutes, then refrigerate them at +4°C overnight.
- The next day, remove the plates from the refrigerator and stir them for 10 minutes.
- Dispense 150µl of Wash solution into each well of the fourth row using the automatic pipettor, then transfer the sections to the fourth row and agitate for 10 minutes. Repeat this step twice again.
- After the third wash, dispense 50µl of each of the two secondary antibodies specified for the protocol into each well of the 7th row. Transfer the sections into the secondary antibodies and wrap the plates with aluminum foil (secondary antibodies bind fluorescent molecules).
- Let the plates stir for 30-60 minutes, then refrigerate them at +4°C overnight.
- The next day, remove the plates from the refrigerator and stir them for 10 minutes. Repeat the three washes with the Wash solution, always ensuring to rewrap the plates in aluminum foil after each step.
- Dispense PBS into each well and transfer the sections into PBS.

*Note: In each well, 2 antibodies must always be dispensed together. The primary antibodies must be produced in two different animal species (e.g., rabbit and mouse), and the secondary antibodies must be directed against each species of origin of the primary antibodies (e.g., anti-rabbit and anti-mouse).

SLIDES MOUNTING:

- Prepare one slide for each skin biopsy. Write the patient's Surname and Name, slide identification code, and sampling site on each slide.
- Place the slide inclined into a Petri dish filled with PBS, with the sections floating in the PBS. Position the Petri dish under the stereomicroscope.
- Using the stereomicroscope and the tip of a needle, transfer the sections from the PBS onto the slide.
- Cover the slides to protect them from light and place them under the hood.
- The following day, under hood protection, dehydrate the slides for 10 minutes in 95% ethanol, followed by 10 minutes in 100% ethanol, and then immerse them in xylene for 5 minutes before beginning the coverslip process.
- Remove the slides from the xylene, apply 8 drops of fluorescence mounting medium to cover the sections, and place the coverslip.
- Allow the slides to dry for at least 6 hours before proceeding with microscope analysis.

- **Working solutions:**

PBS 0,1 M pH 7.4

Dissolve in approximately 950 ml of distilled water:

1.09 g Na₂HPO₄

0.368g of NaH₂PO₄*H₂O

9 g of NaCl.

Adjust the pH of the solution to 7.4 with NaOH 1M (2 g in 50 ml of distilled water).

Make up the final volume to 1l with distilled water and store at 4°C for 6 months.

PBS/Ecosurf (0,3% Ecosurf in PBS 0,1 M pH 7.4)

BLOCK (5% Normal Donkey Serum in PBS/ Ecosurf)

WASH (1% Normal Donkey Serum in PBS/ Ecosurf)

- **Primary antibodies:**

Antibody	Manufacturer	Code	Clonality	Storage
r-PGP	Abcam	ab108986	rabbit mono	aliquots -20°C
m-coll	Millipore	MAB1910	mouse mono	aliquots -20°C

- **Secondary antibodies:**

Antibody	Manufacturer	Code	Specificity	Storage
m-488	Jakson	715-545-150	Anti mouse	aliquots -20°C
r-CY3	Jakson	711-165-152	Anti rabbit	aliquots -20°C

After thawing, dilute aliquots with the WASH solution. Please consider that you'll put two distinct antibodies at the same time in every well or slide (50 µl each). Thus, every antibody must be doubly concentrated before being used and mixed with the other antibody.

- **Antibodies dilutions for free-floating analysis (50 micron):**

Antibody	Final dilution
I°	
r-PGP	1:500
m-Collagen IV	1:1600
II°	
r-CY3	1:800
m-488 AlexaF.	1:400

